

Thorium-Based Energy Production Simulation: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

This paper presents two simulation models to explore the energy production potential of thorium-based nuclear fuels. In the first model, thorium is converted to uranium-233 (U-233) with 50% efficiency, and the energy produced is evaluated. The second simulation targets a scenario with advanced reactor designs and 99% efficiency for thorium to uranium conversion. The results of both models are compared, and theoretical energy production is evaluated in relation to the electricity demand of households in Turkey. The study concludes that advanced simulations can significantly increase energy production by fully utilizing the potential of thorium.

Introduction

The global increase in energy demand has raised interest in nuclear energy. Thorium (Th-232) is a promising fuel source for the future due to its high energy density and abundant reserves. When bombarded by neutrons, thorium-232 is converted into uranium-233 (U-233), a fissile material capable of producing large amounts of energy through nuclear fission. The objective of this study is to simulate the energy production potential of thorium and compare the energy generated under two different efficiency scenarios. The first simulation utilizes a basic conversion model, while the second simulation employs advanced reactor technologies with up to 99% fuel conversion efficiency.

Methodology

Algorithm Development

The simulations are designed to model the neutron capture of thorium, its conversion to uranium-233, and energy production via U-233 fission. Both models follow the steps below:

1. Neutron Capture by Thorium-232: Thorium-232 is converted into thorium-233 (Th-233) upon neutron bombardment.
2. Decay of Thorium-233 to Protactinium-233: Th-233 decays into protactinium-233 (Pa-233).
3. Decay of Protactinium-233 to Uranium-233: Pa-233 decays into uranium-233 (U-233).
4. Fission of Uranium-233: U-233 undergoes fission, releasing energy. The energy per fission is assumed to be 200 MeV.

Calculation Formulas:

- Energy per fission: $E_{\text{fission}} = 200 \text{ MeV}$
- Conversion from MeV to joules: $1 \text{ MeV} = 1.60218 \times 10^{-13} \text{ joules}$
- Neutron capture rate of thorium atoms: $\text{Capture Rate} = \text{neutron_flux} \times \text{cross_section} \times \text{number of thorium atoms}$
- Energy Production: $\text{Energy Produced} = \text{number of fission events} \times E_{\text{fission}}$

Simple Simulation (First Study)

In the first simulation, thorium-232 is assumed to be converted into uranium-233 with 50% efficiency. The neutron flux is kept at basic levels, and the total energy production is evaluated.

```
def thorium_neutron_capture(thorium_atoms, time_step):  
    capture_rate = neutron_flux * capture_cross_section * thorium_atoms  
    thorium_to_th233 = capture_rate * time_step * 0.5 # 50% efficiency  
    return thorium_to_th233
```

Advanced Simulation (Second Study)

In the advanced simulation, thorium is converted to uranium-233 with 99% efficiency, and the fuel cycle operates at 99% efficiency. Additionally, the use of advanced reactor designs, particularly Liquid Fluoride Thorium Reactors (LFTR), is assumed. This model aims to maximize energy production.

```
def thorium_neutron_capture(thorium_atoms, time_step):  
    capture_rate = neutron_flux * capture_cross_section * thorium_atoms  
    thorium_to_th233 = capture_rate * time_step * 0.99 # 99% efficiency  
    return thorium_to_th233
```

Results and Comparison

Results of the First Simulation

In the first simulation, the amount of thorium converted to U-233 was limited, resulting in a total energy production of 2.97 terajoules (TJ). This energy would only be enough to power all households in Turkey for approximately 5 minutes.

Results of the Advanced Simulation

In the advanced simulation, where 99% of thorium is converted to U-233 and the reactor operates at maximum efficiency, the total energy production reached 679.67 petajoules (PJ). This amount of energy could supply the electricity needs of Turkey for approximately 2 years.

Results Comparison

Simulation	Efficiency	Total Energy (Joules)	Equivalent Power for Turkish Households
Basic Simulation	50%	2.97 TJ	5 minutes
Advanced Simulation	99%	679.67 PJ	2 years

Discussion

The first simulation demonstrates that even with limited thorium conversion efficiency, a certain amount of energy can still be produced. However, more efficient reactor systems are needed to fully harness the potential of thorium. The advanced simulation significantly increases energy production by utilizing advanced reactor designs and optimizing the fuel cycle.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the energy production potential of thorium-based nuclear fuels under two different efficiency models. Advanced reactor technologies significantly enhance energy production by utilizing thorium's full potential. These findings suggest that thorium could play a significant role in sustainable energy production in the future.

References

1. G. F. James, 'The Use of Thorium in Nuclear Energy Production,' Energy Journal, 2022.
2. W. M. Stacey, 'Nuclear Reactor Physics,' John Wiley & Sons, 2007.